

Article

Concept and Implications of Empowerment of Rural Women in North-East India: A Case Study

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Abstract

There are a variety of understandings of the term empowerment due to its widespread usage. There could be statistical finding indicating improvements in indicators of gender equality, but unless the intervening process affecting the involved women is investigated, one can

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not be sure that the improvements of statistical indicators are due to empowerment. For example, style of living of a person may show a high standard but he/she may not be empowered in the true sense. Empowerment can be defined in terms of specific activities or end results because it involves a process whereby women can freely analyze, develop and voice their needs and interests. The study focuses on the process and nature of empowerment in khasi society in Meghalaya and general and tribal women in Tripura.

Most of the states in India are patrilineal but in Meghalaya is matrilineal. However, it may not imply that the women are more empowered than men in Meghalaya. The khasi society of Meghalaya is such a society, commonly known as matrilineal where female folks determine authority, title, inheritance, and residence after marriage and succession. So, it is presumed that the right of the society is already established and they do not require any special effort for their rights. But the question is whether they are aware about the social, economic and other issues as compared to the awareness of male.

Therefore, a question may arise whether in Khasi Tribe the status of empowerment of women is ascribed or prescribed by the society. In Meghalaya the female, normally inherit the property and holds the keys to social and economic activities.

However, in Tripura, we observed many women to take part in political activities and they represent in the panchayat due to the 73rd Constitutional amendment. The 73rd Constitutional amendment, which says that one-third seats should be reserved for women, has not yet been introduced since panchayat system does not exist there, and women are not generally involved in the political activities.

This paper is thus an attempt to examine the nature and process of empowerment of rural women in the two opposing states namely, Meghalaya and Tripura.

Introduction

The simple dictionary meaning of the word empowerment is giving somebody power or authority to act. Yet it has got its own significance. It has beyond this simple meaning that prompted the present study.

The Oxford Dictionary (1962: 265) defines the term 'empowerment' as a process of 'enabling'. Thus it may be described as a "a process in which individuals, groups or communities become able to take control of their circumstances and achieve their own goals, thereby being able to work towards maximizing the quality of their lives (Adams, 1990:43).

The Oxford Dictionary (1994) further defined 'Empowerment' as the process of 'bestowing power upon' or 'to invest someone legally or formally with

power'. It can however, be contradicted 'as "true power can not be bestowed, it comes from within" (Rowlands, 1992:52).

Mohanty (2000:16) describes empowerment as "the process of setting the right environment and structure and creating circumstances where people can use their faculties and abilities to fully actualize their potential'. Thus empowerment facilitates change and enables a person (who may be relatively powerless) to gain control over his/her life through raising awareness, taking action, and working so as to fully actualize his/her inherent potential'. Hence, "empowerment is gaining the capacity to act and having influence over the situation. It can be measured, in one way, as the extent of control over the decision making process in the relevant socio-political and economic structures' (Verma, 2006: 4)

Empowerment is about people - both women and men - taking control over their lives: becoming conscious of their own situation and position, setting their own agenda, creating space for themselves, gaining skills, building self-confidence, solving problems, and developing self-reliance. It is not only a social and political process, but an individual one as well - and it is not only a process but an outcome to.

Outsiders cannot empower women: only women can empower themselves, to make choices or to speak out on their own behalf. However, institutions, NGOs and Government agencies, can support

processes that increase women's self-confidence, develop their self-reliance, and help them set their own agenda.

Such empowerment of the poor and disadvantaged women would lead to benefit at two levels - one, direct benefits to the individual women and women's groups; and two, ripple-effected development benefits for other poor families, the community and the village as a whole.

Empowerment of women is essentially a broader concept heralding a shift from unjust to just, subservient to successful, passive to active ability and entity for women. In the broader context, empowerment of women refers to questioning social, economic and political discrepancies and distortions in terms of gender.

By process of empowerment we mean activities through which the women get access to power so that their wishes are materialised. It is the complex interplay of various factors like physical, social, economic, political, psychological, and attitudinal and so on. However, 'Empowerment' has different meaning to different actors in the development field. The issue of women's empowerment no doubt is closely associated with women's development, but unfortunately there was no such constructive thinking about women's empowerment in India till Fifth Five Year Plan (1974-79) at government level. Of course, the national committee on

the status of women was set up in 1971 before the declaration of Women Decade. This committee submitted their report "Towards Equality" in 1974. Also almost each state has one women's commission to look after the problems and grievances of the women.

In recent years, the empowerment of women has become a popular and much discussed issue, but the very term 'empowerment' was buzzword since 1960's. Since 1990, empowerment of women has become a slogan, a craze and almost in every literature and reference to women's issues and efforts of women's development programme.

The year 2001 was declared as the "International Women's Empowerment Year" by the United Nations. Simultaneously the Government of India had also recognized the same year as 'Women's Empowerment' year.

The issue of empowerment of women has been much discussed at various levels to find out the solution to age old problem of gender discrimination, exploitation of women and for the upliftment of their status and position in the society. In terms of income, women are poorer than men because more households headed by women fall below the income poverty line than households headed by men (HDR, 1997).

This paper is thus an attempt to examine the nature and process of empowerment of rural women in the two

opposing states namely, Meghalaya and Tripura.

In Meghalaya, the society is commonly known as the matrilineal and the society in Tripura is primarily known as patrilineal. However a survey by the author in two villages of each state shows some contradictory results. In two villages outside Shillong, Meghalaya we found that around two-third of the families are headed by the males though these families are predominantly tribal.

Now even in Tripura female-headed households are commonly found in rural areas, especially among the tribal communities.

In Meghalaya the female normally inherit the property and holds the key to social and economic activities. So here a question arises whether the male-headed households are just for the sake of management or the male also dominates in the decision-making in different spheres and derives major benefits out of different activities. It may also be a fact that the females here never bothered about their holding in the society, as their position is already secured in different spheres.

However in Tripura we found many women to take part in political activities and they represent in the panchayats in due proportion as is given in the Constitution though the men normally dominate in different activities and decision-making. Even in most cases, though women are elected due to reservation, they actually

express and convey the views of their male counterpart (husband, father etc). So they became the hands of their male counterpart in socio-political activities.

Where as, in Meghalaya we found hardly any woman to take part in political activities and even in the Dorbars (the local self-governing institutions). However, with the development of socio-economic conditions and influence of other social groups every society goes through a change over time and through active participation women learn and increasingly acquire holding in different sphere.

The Concept of empowerment

Empowerment is the term generally used to describe a process by which powerless people become conscious of their own situation and organize collectively to gain greater access to public service or to the benefits of economic growth. Empowerment can be studied in two ways. First, empowerment in general related to the poor or those who are powerless. Second is the empowerment of women.

In this context we are interested to study the empowerment of women in rural areas.

Empowerment of women is essential to emancipate women from the social evils called traditional and cultural customs. Women are marginalized over years together at various stages, and also they are branded as weaker and are kept aside from reaching the front stage. In this

context, empowerment is required to increase awareness and capacity building for their greater participation in the decision-making.

In this line, we may define "Empowerment of women as the redistribution of power that enable thus to challenge patriarchal ideology and the male dominance. It is both a process and an end result of it also.

This process not only increases their capacity; but also enable them face new challenges in the overall development of the household and also to contribute to the local community development also.

Empowerment as a concept is a result of the process which enable a individual to know about herself / himself, what she / he wants, express it, try to get it and fulfill their needs by enhanced confidence, awareness, mobility, choices, control over resources and decision making power. The process, which enables an individual to gain the above qualities, is called empowerment.

The process of gaining control over resources, ideology and self, which determine power, can be called empowerment.

When we apply this definition for empowerment of women, it is clear that women do not have power since they don't have control over resources. Even if they have, it is only to some extent over some resources. This power is limited by

patriarchal norms, customs, traditions and social values imposed on them.

In the family male person is considered as breadwinner, physical and financial assets are in his name and control, naturally power is in his hands. Women being deprived of access to and control over resources are denied of power. Even in the case of community, public property resources, institution and political power is concentrated in the hands of men. Women are kept out of this domain.

Concept of Different aspects of empowerment:

The social empowerment aimed at:

- A) Equal status, participation and powers of decision-making of women in household
- B) Equal status, participation and powers of decision-making in community and village
- C) Increased status, participation and powers of decision-making in democratic institutions

Economic empowerment aimed at:

- A) Greater access to financial resources outside household
- B) Reduced vulnerability of the poor women to crisis - famine, flood, riots, etc.
- C) Significant increase in the women's own income

D) Equal access and control over resources at the household level

Financial self reliance of women

E) Capacity Building (is a strategy and an end in itself) through better awareness on health, education, environment, etc.

F) Improved Functional literacy

G) Better communication skills and leadership qualities

I) Self-help and mutual help

Political Empowerment aimed at:

A) Tend to take up basic issues like water, health facilities and

education

B) Care for or look after women's problem predominantly

C) Fight for their rights and among women's laws and acts to suits their

own benefits.

D) Voice their grievances effectively for redressal.

Method of study

Process of empowerment of women here has been studied through primary survey in four villages (two from Tripura and two from Meghalaya). These villages are Beltali and Kalitila of Paschim Noabadi Gram Panchayat under Jirania

block, West Tripura district and Ringkseh and Kynton-u-mon under East Khasi Hill district of Mawlyngknang block. The villages are chosen purposively on consideration of conveniences, such as access and communication, security, expenditure involved in survey etc. However most of the features of the states have much in common in the selected villages of the respective states.

For the purpose of analysis, first of all we have considered all the 587 households of the selected villages in both the states. The ratio of male and female-headed families in the selected areas was found to be 3: 1 and 1.6: 1 in Tripura and Meghalaya respectively. Though the state of Tripura is primarily patrilineal still we find almost $\frac{1}{4}$ th of the selected families are females headed. Though the society of Meghalaya is commonly known as matrilineal, more than two third of the families run by males and only around $\frac{1}{3}$ rd are headed by females. Then question naturally arises whether the society of Meghalaya also gradually approaching towards patrilineal and the dominance of female has been still prevailing in the same rate or not.

Then, we have stratified the families according to the characteristics of sex of family head, caste, occupation, education etc. and finally chosen 204 households. Using stratified random sampling 36 male headed households out of 110 and 19 female headed households out of 27 in Beltali, are selected and 36 male headed households out of 154 and 18 female

headed households out of 39 have been selected in Kalitila in Tripura. In Meghalaya from the village Ringkseh, 25 male-headed households out of 73 and 20 female-headed households out of 46 have been chosen randomly, whereas in Kyton-u-mon 22 male-headed households out of 102 and 28 female-headed households out of 36 have been chosen randomly.

Data have been collected, from the finally chosen households, on different aspects like family size, sex, education, caste, occupation, income and expenditure etc. i.e. on social, cultural, economical, political, religious and psychological aspects. From

that information we tried to understand the process of empowerment by analysing the data.

The study is mainly exploratory in nature.

Property by Inheritance

In Meghalaya 21 out of 48 female heads received property through inheritance, whereas in Tripura only 7 out of 37 female heads inherited property. (Table 1) In case of Meghalaya, proportion of male heads also inherits property like that of female heads, which is clear from the table.

Table 1: Distribution of households by received any kind of property by inheritance

State	Sex	Received Property by inheritance			Sub - total	Total
		Received	Not Received	Others		
Meghalaya	Male	21	26	0	47	95
	Female	21	27	0	48	
Tripura	Male	39	30	3	72	109
	Female	7	28	2	37	
Grand Total	Male	60	56	3	119	204
	Female	28	55	2	85	

Social empowerment:

Through the participation in different social, economic problems and also become aware of their rights through discourses of interaction. The more such participation the less will be the shyness and women are more encouraged to do so when they become educated, which is described through the observation in the table below.

Membership in a club / community centre / social organisation /NGO:

It is observed from Table 2 below that 83.33% of total female heads of households of these states are neither member of any club, Community Centre or Social Organisation. The above percentage for Meghalaya is almost 85% and for 81%. In Tripura women seems to be more interested in such interactive programmes and social functions, which is clear from their higher membership of such organisations. Comparatively female heads have lesser tendency to be member of such organisations than their male counterpart in both the states. But in Tripuras the tendency of females to be member and participate in such organisations is more than that of Meghalaya and the tendency is more in the educated group than the non- educated sections of population.

Table 2: Distribution of the head of the households by their membership in Club/Community Centre/Social Organization

State	Sex	Literacy Status	Member of Club/Community Centre/Social Organisation		Sub total	Total
			Yes	No		
Meghalaya	Male	Illiterate	0	7	47	95
		< Madhyamik	6	20		

		> Madhyamik	6	8		
	Female	Illiterate	1	17	48	
		< Madhyamik	1	22		
		> Madhyamik	0	7		
Tripura	Male	Illiterate	1	9	72	109
		< Madhyamik	11	39		
		> Madhyamik	4	8		
	Female	Illiterate	9	13	37	
		< Madhyamik	7	8		
		> Madhyamik	0	0		
Grand Total			46	158		204

It is clear from the table below that among the female-headed households very little number of female-headed households (2 out of 48 female-headed households only) is a member of Club or Community Centre or Social Organisation in Meghalaya. And 16 out of 37 female headed households responded that they are the members of Club or Community Centre or Social Organisation. But in case of male headed households in Meghalaya the percentage of members is more than the percentage of female head numbers of the female headed households. But in Tripura the numbers of positive responses from both the male and female-headed households are more or less the similar.

It is clear from Table 5 that in Meghalaya 12 and 2 positive responses have been obtained from the total 47 male headed and 48 female headed households respectively. But in Tripura 16 out of 72 male headed households and 4 out of 37 female headed households have responded in positive direction.

Table 3: Distribution of households by the membership in a club/community centre/social organization/NGO

State	Sex	Member of club/community center/social organization/NGO		Sub total	Total
		Yes	No		
Meghalaya	Male	12	35	47	95
	Female	2	46	48	
Tripura	Male	16	56	72	109
	Female	16	21	37	
Total	Male	28	91	119	204
	Female	18	67	85	

Participation in a meeting/function out side village

Meghalaya's women are more advanced than Tripura's women regarding the participation in meeting/function without the permission of male members of their family.

In Meghalaya 43 female-headed households out of 48 female-headed households participate in a meeting/ function alone out side village. In case of Tripura this number is 15 out of 37(Table 4).Even though some women are members of different social institutions, they are

not free to choose to participate because of customs, insecurity and other social bindings. Whereas in Meghalaya, women whether educated or not, have no such bindings and can move freely.

Table 4: Distribution of the female headed households accordingly participation in a meeting/function outside the village

State	Literacy Status	Participation in meeting/function			Total
		Alone	With men or women from the same or other family	Others	
Meghalaya	Illiterate	17	1	0	48
	< Madhyamik	19	2	2	
	> Madhyamik	7	0	0	
Tripura	Illiterate	9	1	12	37
	< Madhyamik	6	0	9	
	> Madhyamik	0	0	0	
Grand Total	Illiterate	26	2	12	85
	< Madhyamik	25	2	11	

	> Madhyami k	7	0	0	
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Psychological empowerment

Training Programme towards Self-sufficiency

Training programme sometimes help women gaining confidence and idea through the interactions with others. From Table 5, it is clear that maximum number of households in both the states think that the training programme for women is for imbibing elements in the mindset as well as improving quality to acquire self-sufficiency. If we look at the data minutely, we find more percentage of female in Meghalaya is in favour of such training programme than in Tripura though the female of Meghalaya are already acquainted with most of the household and outside activities than the females of Tripura. If we combine both the states together, then it has been seen that 109 male headed households out of the total 119 male-headed households and 69 female heads out of 85 female-headed households think that the training programme for women is for self-sufficiency.

Table 5: Distribution of households by the perception of the head of household whether training programme for women is towards self-sufficiency

State	Sex	Training Programme towards self-sufficiency				Sub total	Total
		Yes	No	Not Sure	No Idea		
Meghalaya	Male	43	0	0	4	47	95
	Female	39	0	0	9	48	

Tripura	Male	66	3	1	2	72	109
	Female	30	1	4	2	37	
Grand Total	Male	109	3	1	6	119	204
	Female	69	1	4	11	85	
	Total	178	4	5	17	204	

Visit to the Nearest Town

Regarding the fact for visit the nearest town with out the permission of male members Meghalaya's women are more advanced than Tripura's women. In Meghalaya 43 female-headed households out of the total 48 female-headed households visits the nearest town without the permission of their male members and out of these 43 female-headed households 33 female headed holds are literate.

But in Tripura only 17 female headed households out of the total 37 female headed households visit the nearest town alone without the permission of their male members and out of these 17, 14 female headed households are literate.

Thus it is a clear fact that women of Meghalaya are much more free and independent in their decision making process compared to women of the concerned other state.

Table 6: Distribution of female headed households by visit to the nearest town without the permission of male members

State	Age Group	Visit to nearest town			Total
		Alone	With men or women from the same or other family	Others	
Meghalaya	20-40	10	0	2	48
	41-60	17	2	0	
	> 60	16	1	0	
Tripura	20-40	3	0	0	37
	41-60	8	0	8	
	> 60	6	1	11	
Grand Total	20-40	13	0	2	85
	41-60	25	2	8	
	> 60	22	2	11	

Freedom to move outside Village:

It is also another aspect of social or psychological status of women. In Meghalaya, all the heads of the female headed households have freedom to move outside the village.. But in the state of Tripura, only 11 female-headed households out of 37 female-headed households have freedom to move outside village and 19 female-headed households have no such freedom to move outside village. So in this respect we can say that Meghalaya's women are more advanced than Tripura's women. Even the illiterate women in Meghalaya have the freedom to decide in matter

of moving outside the village which clearly indicate that the literacy status is not the only determining factor of empowerment. But this view remains confined to some specific areas.

Table 7: Distribution of female headed households by their freedom to move outside village

State	Village	Literacy Status	Freedom to move outside village			Total	
			Have Freedom	Haven't Freedom	No Comments		
Meghalaya	Ringkeeh	Illiterate	2	0	0	20	
		<Madhyamik	15	0	0		
		>Madhyamik	3	0	0		
	Subtotal			20	0	0	28
	Kytonu-mon	Illiterate	16	0	0	48	
		<Madhyamik	8	0	0		
		>Madhyamik	4	0	0		
	Subtotal			28	0	0	
	Total			48	0	0	
	Tripura	Beltali	Illiterate	5	6	2	19
<Madhyamik			1	2	3		

		>Madhya mik	0	0	0	
	Subtotal		6	8	5	18
Kalitila	Illiterate		4	4	1	
	<Madhya mik		1	7	1	
	>Madhya mik		0	0	0	37
	Subtotal		5	11	2	
	Total		11	19	7	
Grand Total			59	19	7	85

Equal pay for men and women for the same work:

It is found from Table 8 that in Tripura 75% male heads of the total male-headed households and 73% female heads of the total female-headed households think that there should be equal pay for men and women for the same work. But in Meghalaya the above percentages are 26% and 35% respectively for male-headed households and female-headed households.

Table 8: Distribution of the households on the opinion of equal pay for men and women for the same work

State	Village	Sex	Ag	Thinks about Equal Pay	Subtot	Tot
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			e Gr ou p	Agre e	Not Agre e	Not Sure	al	al
Megh alaya	Ringks eh	Ma le	20- 40	1	7	0	25 (55.56)	45 (47 .37)
			41- 60	1	6	1		
			>6 0	2	7	0		
		Fe ma le	20- 40	3	1	0	20 (44.44)	
			41- 60	2	6	0		
			>6 0	0	8	0		
	Kyton- u-mon	Ma le	20- 40	3	4	1	22 (44)	50 (52 .63)
			41- 60	3	7	0		
			>6 0	2	2	0		
		Fe ma le	20- 40	4	4	0	28 (56)	
			41- 60	5	6	0		
			>6 0	3	4	2		

	Total	Male		12(25.5)	33(70.2)	2(4.26)	47(49.47)	95 (46.57)
		Female		17(35.4)	29(60.4)	2(4.17)	48(50.53)	
Tripura	Beltali	Male	20-40	11	1	0	36 (65.45)	55 (50.46)
			41-60	9	6	1		
			>60	3	5	0		
		Female	20-40	0	0	0	19 (34.55)	
			41-60	7	2	1		
			>60	7	0	2		
	Kalitila	Male	20-40	18	0	0	36 (66.67)	54 (49.54)
			41-60	11	3	1		
			>60	2	1	0		
		Female	20-40	2	1	0	18 (33.33)	
41-60			5	2	0			

			>6 0	6	1	1		
	Total	Male		54 (75)	16 (22.22)	2 (2.78)	72 (66.06)	109 (53.43)
		Female		27 (72.97)	6 (16.22)	4 (10.81)	37 (33.94)	
Grand Total		Male		66 (55.46)	49 (41.18)	4 (3.36)	119 (58.33)	204 (100)
		Female		44 (51.76)	35 (41.18)	6 (7.06)	85 (41.67)	
		Total		110 (53.92)	84 (41.18)	10 (4.90)	204 (100)	

Reservation of women seats for members in Gram Panchayat

The opinion about the reservation of women seats for members in Gram Panchayat is very bad in Meghalaya states. Out of 95 households 61 household's opinion about the above is very bad in this state. But in Tripura the result is totally opposite. In this state maximum number of household's opinion about the reservation of women seats for members in Gram Panchayat is good or very good. Not a single household's opinion is very bad in Tripura state. (Table 9)

Table 9: Distribution of households by their opinion about the reservation of women seats for members in Gram Panchayat

State	Sex	Opinion						Subtotal	Total
		Very bad	Bad	Not so bad	Good	Very Good	No idea		
Meghalaya	Male	32	4	5	1	0	5	47	95
	Female	29	9	1	1	0	8	48	
Tripura	Male	0	0	10	30	32	0	72	109
	Female	0	0	9	17	11	0	37	
Grand Total	Male	32	4	15	31	32	5	119	204
	Female	29	9	10	18	11	8	85	
	Total	61	13	25	49	43	13	204	

Concluding remarks

Women in rural Meghalaya are more empowered in many respect compared to that of Tripura. Because of property inheritance, better control over resources, ability to work in different fields and participation in different social activities they feel more independent and can move freely without any fear.

The Khasi of Meghalaya is a matrilineal society and inheritance and clan membership is organized around the mother's house headed by the grandmother who lives with her unmarried daughters, her youngest

daughter (even if she is married), and her youngest daughter's children. Though Khasi women do not generally assume the roles held by men in patriarchal societies they always live in households in which they or their mother have authority over most household decisions.

Women in rural Meghalaya are not well aware of their political rights. To them political decision-making is not much important, though body like Dorbar is much powerful but their participation in such bodies is also minimal. Most of them do not believe in reservation in the local bodies. Rather they like to devote more on their social and economic activities for their welfare.

They are free from any limitation and can participate freely in any function of social and religious importance. Also they can move freely without the company of male or others.

In Tripura however women are conscious about their status and position but due to social customs, limitations of security their status is relatively lower especially of the uneducated, deserted and widow groups. Hence they are relatively more dependent on their male counterpart. Though they are politically more conscious and take part in different social and organisational activities, which are limited within a particular boundary and in many cases even within their households.

Hence, any strategy for women's empowerment must aim at creating the power among men and women to collaborate with each other in order to achieve their potentials as human beings which must lead both the sexes to enjoy freedom.

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